

**CORRELATION BETWEEN TIME MANAGEMENT AND SELF
ACTUALIZATION AMONG B.ED. STUDENTS**

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Abstract : -

The aim of this research paper was to determine the correlation between Time Management and Self Actualization of B.Ed.students. Time Management is the process of planning and exercising conscious control over the amount of time spent on specific activities especially to increase effectiveness and productivity. Self Actualization reflects the intrinsic belief in the self .i.e. the overall opinion and value of a person .Description survey method was adopted in this study. This study revealed that the B.Ed.students is having a high level of Time management and self actualization. As this study proves, there is a significant correlation between Time management and self actualization.

Introduction: - This paper is intended to study the level of Time management among B.Ed. college students and its correlation with self actualization. Now a day's many college students are spending less time in studying .Many B.Ed. college students are giving very less importance to Time management. Due to which the valuable time of students is being wasted in visiting too much to social networking sites like whatsapp, face book etc. Today college students are prepared less for college level work than their predecessor's once they get into colleges they tend to spend less time for studying and would like to do jobs and other things.

Time management plays a vital role in improving student's academic performance. Each and every student should have Time management ability which includes

setting goals and priorities, using time management mechanism and being organized in using time. There is no one right way to manage your time, however it is important to get to know our self so we can make good decisions about how to use our time.

This is the era of globalization with information technology as its focus. Professionalization is the key to achieve this. It becomes imperative to develop new and varied skills. Our extremely important human characteristics affected by social interaction and physical activity is self actualization. In order to adopt and learn to new skills each student must have high level of self actualization in this competitive word. Student's emotions are important because their thoughts, feelings and moods affect their subsequent motivational behavior and learning. It is terribly unfortunate that students who are bright and competent but lacking in self actualization will often shelf themselves and withdraws from programs of academic or vocational success, prematurely. Therefore the investigators have tried to focus on the kind of Time management and self actualization among B.Ed. students.

Time Management: - Time Management is the act or process of planning and exercising conscious control over the amount of time spent on specific activities especially to increase effectiveness, efficiency or productivity. Initially time management referred to just business or work activities, but eventually the term broadened to include personal activities as well as educational systems. Most of students tend to be activity oriented rather than result oriented. Consequently they spend their days in a flurry of activity with little or nothing to show for it. They are spending quality time on inconsequential activities that are not important. Following are some tools and methods have been listed below to improve student's time management.

1. Eliminate Waste
2. Delegate
3. Help Others Prudently
4. Maintain a Diary
5. Cost Your Time
6. Allocate Time for Long Term Objectives and Goals
7. Your Work Priorities
8. Maintain To Do Lists.
9. Set Goals.

Self Actualization: - A phenomenological theorist who emphasized development on the self was Abraham Maslow. Maslow believed that each person has essential

nature that ‘presses’ to emerge like the ‘press’ within an acorn to become an oak tree. In this view we all have higher – level growth needs such as the need for self actualization and understanding of our selves but that these higher needs (physiological needs, safety needs, needs for love and ‘belongingness’ and self – esteem needs) are satisfied. The growth needs, Maslow believed help marks us distinctly human. Maslow stressed this “the human being is not a white rat” and emphasized that “man has higher and transcendent nature.” Maslow (1967) found that self – actualized people share some distinguishing characteristics as follows.

1. They were open to experience vividly, selflessly with full concentration and total absorption.
2. They were in tune with themselves, their inner beings.
3. They were spontaneous, autonomous, and independent with a fresh, appreciation of people and events.
4. They were dedicated, fully and creatively to some cause outside themselves.
5. They devoted total effort to their goals, wanting to be first – rate or at least as good as they could be.

Statement of the Problem: The present problem is stated as “Correlation between Time management and Self Actualization among B.Ed. students.”

Objectives: -

To find out the correlation between Time management and Self Actualization of B.Ed. college students.

Hypotheses: -

1. There is no significant correlation between Time management and Self Actualization of Male B.Ed. college students.
2. There is no significant correlation between Time management and Self Actualization of Female B.Ed. college students
3. There is no significant correlation between Time management and Self Actualization of all B.Ed. college students.

Methodology: - Looking at the nature of the study and variables, descriptive survey method was adopted in this study.

Sample: - A total sample of 60 B.Ed. college students was drawn from Jalgaon district of Maharashtra state. All these B.Ed. colleges of Jalgaon district are affiliated to North Maharashtra University, Jalgaon. The sample was selected by using simple random technique. The sample consists of 33 Female and 27 Male students. The sample forms a representative sample of entire population.

Tools used:-

1. Time Management Scale: - Developed and standardized by D.N.Sansanwal and Meenakshi Parashar (Indore). This tool is suitable for self – report measures of Time Management. It contains 36 statements on a five – point scale.

2. Self Actualization Inventory: - Developed and standardized by K.N.Sharma (Jaipur). This tool contains 75 statements on a three – point scale. This tool is suitable for measures of Self Actualization.

Both tools are standardized and having reliability and validity.

Statistical Technique Used: - For analysis of the obtained data quantitative techniques like coefficient of correlation was used.

Analysis of variables: -

Table 1: Coefficients of Correlation between Time management and Self Actualization of Male B.Ed. college students.

Null Hypothesis 1: There is no significant correlation between Time management and Self Actualization of Male B.Ed. college students.

Variables	N (Male)	Calculated 'r' value	df	Table 'r' value	Comparison between Calculated 'r' value & Table 'r' value	Significance at 0.05 level	Null Hypothesis
Time Management & Self Actualization	27	+0.672	25	+0.396	Calculated 'r' value > Table 'r' Value	Significant	Rejected

Table 1 shows that, the Correlation between variables Time management and Self Actualization of Male B.Ed. college students is positive and significant at 0.05 levels of significance. So null hypothesis “There is no significant correlation between Time management and Self Actualization of Male B.Ed. college students.” is rejected.

Table 2: Coefficients of Correlation between Time management and Self Actualization of Female B.Ed. college students.

Null Hypothesis 2: There is no significant correlation between Time management and Self Actualization of Female B.Ed. college students.

Variables	N (Female)	Calculated 'r' value	df	Table 'r' value	Comparison between Calculated 'r' value & Table 'r' value	Significance at 0.05 level	Null Hypothesis
Time Management & Self Actualization	33	+0.731	31	+0.333	Calculated 'r' value > Table 'r' Value	Significant	Rejected

Table 2 shows that, the Correlation between variables Time management and Self Actualization of Male B.Ed. college students is positive and significant at 0.05 levels of significance. So null hypothesis “There is no significant correlation between Time management and Self Actualization of female B.Ed. college students.” is rejected.

Table 3: Coefficients of Correlation between Time management and Self Actualization of all B.Ed. college students.

Null Hypothesis 3: There is no significant correlation between Time management and Self Actualization of Female all B.Ed. college students.

Variables	N (All)	Calculated 'r' value	df	Table 'r' value	Comparison between Calculated 'r' value & Table 'r' value	Significance at 0.05 level	Null Hypothesis
Time Management & Self Actualization	60	+0.784	58	+0.254	Calculated 'r' value > Table 'r' Value	Significant	Rejected

Table 3 shows that, the Correlation between variables Time management and Self Actualization of all B.Ed. college students is positive and significant at 0.05 levels of significance. So null hypothesis “There is no significant correlation between Time management and Self Actualization of all B.Ed. college students.” is rejected.

Major findings of the study: -

1. There is a highly significant and positive correlation between Time management and Self Actualization among Male B.Ed. college students.
2. There is a highly significant and positive correlation between Time management and Self Actualization among Female B.Ed. college students.
3. There is a highly significant and positive correlation between Time management and Self Actualization among all B.Ed. college students.

Conclusion: - It can be concluded that B.Ed. students are having considerably higher level of Time management and Self Actualization due to the current educational system. This demands practical – oriented study. As this study proves that there is a significant correlation between Time management and Self Actualization it is important to maintain an environment that favors the development of Self Actualization of the students at home, school, colleges which in turn will encourage a holistic development of the learners. Such holistic development of individuals encourages them to become renowned scholars who are responsible for

making the Society & Nation better.

Recommendations: - The present investigations have given strength and focus to the fact that Self Actualization of B.Ed. students have a positive significant correlation with their Time management. It is recommended that heads of institutions who admit students various courses should bear this fact that in mind and prefer students whose Self Actualization is high. It is also recommended that pre-service training of teachers could include Self Actualization development program. Seminars on Time management and Self Actualization could be arranged. The nation needs man and women who could 'will' 'intend' and decide on their own. Present research attempted would help the nation to grow further.

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